

OXFORD BROOKES UNIVERSITY

RESEARCH ANALYSIS PROJECT

BUSINESS & FINANCIAL DATA ANALYSIS OF TOYOTA MOTOR CORPORATION 2017-2019

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Part - 1

**Research Objectives and Overall
Approach**

Topic 8

Analysis and Evaluation of Business and Financial Performance of Toyota Motor Corporation for the years 2017, 2018 and 2019

Reason for choosing the Topic:

As an ACCA (Association of Chartered Certified Accountants) pursuant, I decided to apply for B.Sc. in Applied Accounting and business offered by Oxford Brookes University. So, when I was given an array of topics to choose from, this particular topic caught my attention because of my undying passion towards financial analysis.

My past acquired knowledge during this certification required me to complete 2 strategic examinations which consisted of almost all the topics relevant for this research project namely, SBL (Strategic Business Leader) and SBR (Strategic Business Reporting). This has enabled me to sharpen my skills in the field and I hope that by the end of this project, I would have enhanced my skillset further.

Reason for Choosing the Company:

The reason for choosing Toyota Motor Corporation is my love towards automobiles from a very young age. Toyota being the worlds' richest and the largest manufacturer of automobiles, I instantly knew that my research project has to be done on Toyota.

Toyota is known for its' invention of the Just-In-Time(JIT) inventory approach in the early 1970's by Taiichi Ohno whose main aim was to meet customer demands within minimum days which was later adopted by most of the manufacturing industries we know of today. (Parashar, 2016a)

Industry Analysis

Overview of Toyota

After the Great Kanto Earthquake in Tokyo, Japan in the year 1923, the railway system was devastated. This created the demand for automobiles for transportation in the country which led the government of Japan to import automobiles from an American supplier, Ford Motors. Due to a high demand of automobiles, Ford Motors established Ford Japan and General Motors (GM) – Japan. (Toyota, 2020a)

As the usage of automobiles increased, Kiichiro Toyoda, the son of the founder of Toyoda Automatic Loom Works took 10 years to study the production facilities of Ford Motor Corp., to research and to establish Toyota Motor Corporation on 1st September 1933 which was a spin-off of his father's Toyota Industries. (Toyota, 2020b)

Now Toyota has about 608 subsidiaries and 63 equity affiliates, of which most of them are in manufacturing of vehicles and they still produce sewing machines and looms. It employs around 370,870 employees as of 2019 and it is listed in Tokyo Stock Exchange, London Stock Exchange (LSE) and New York Stock Exchange (NYSE) (Toyota, 2019)

Toyota is the world's No. 1 automaker with a market capitalization of \$202.3 billion as of 2019. It aims to optimize the carbon footprint by reducing carbon emissions of cars by 90% by 2050 and this mission is called Challenge2050. Toyota is also aiming to build "Woven City" at the foot of Mt. Fuji, Japan which will be a 175 acre high tech sensor laden metropolis. This project is scheduled to start in 2021. (Toyota Newsroom, 2020), (Toyota, 2020c)

For the United States, Toyota plays a big role in the economy, by being a generator of around 470,100 jobs, billions of dollars have been invested by Toyota for research centres, manufacturing units, 7.1 billion capital, Toyota has spent more than \$700 million for charity in U.S (Dziczek, et al., 2016)

About the Industry:

Automobile industry is extremely dynamic, highly competitive and innovative. Not only does it consist of the manufacturing of cars and spare parts but also reselling, servicing and various other related services. The Economy of many countries such as the United States, Japan and most of the European countries like France, Germany, Italy etc. depends on this industry. (John Bell Rae, 2020)

Toyota generated revenue of approximately 30 trillion Japanese Yen or more than 280 million dollars alone in the year 2019 which is the highest among the other manufacturers in the industry. This is for the first time in Japan a company has reached this number. (japantimes.co.jp, 2019)

The following chart illustrates the number of vehicles sold worldwide:

(oica.net, 2019)

The overall sales of cars have fallen in the year 2019. This was a drastic fall after 2008 and the experts have said that it is much worse than the previous one. There were several reasons behind this fall, the most significant was the falling demand in China. (Raimonde, 2019)

(focus2move.com, 2020)

The Chart above illustrates the market share of the automobile companies in 2019, Toyota being in the 2nd place with a 11.4% of the market share.

RAP Objectives

Below are the RAP objectives:

- To perform Business analysis of Toyota using PEST and SWOT analysis.
- To analyse the financial performance of Toyota using Ratio analysis for the FY-2017, 2018 and 2019.
- To performance comparison of Toyota by its competitor Honda for three financial years FY-2017, 2018 and 2019.
- To provide a conclusion and recommendation for the business analysis performed.

RAP Framework:

The discussion of this project begins with the reason for choosing this topic and Toyota as a company for analysis. It includes the history of how Toyota, its achievements through the years to become the pioneer in the industry and its future goals. It also includes a thorough study about the industry Toyota operates in and the market share it holds.

The second section of this project consists of the sources of information used and the inherent limitations of using these sources. It also consists of an overview of the business and accounting techniques used for the analysis of the financial and non-financial data and the ethical considerations used while carrying out this study.

The third section of this project is a thorough analysis of Toyota with its competitor Honda using the various techniques prescribed by RAP. After the analysis, the project has been concluded with a summary and recommendations.

Part – 2

Sources of Information, Accounting and Business Analytical Techniques and Ethical Considerations

Information:

Information is the data that is accurate, timely and specific to the users (i.e. organisations) processed in such a manner that it becomes useful for them in decision making. (businessdictionary.com, 2020)

Sources of Information:**Annual report:**

Annual report of Toyota and Honda for the financial years 2017,2018 and 2019 will be used for most of the financial and non-financial data used in the project. Annual report has most of the data required for this project. The reliability of the Annual report is enhanced if it is audited externally by independent, well-known auditors.

Company's Website:

Company's website is a source where most of the information I gathered including the annual report as well. It also contains most of the other relevant data such as the company's future plans, history of the company, products, . www.global.toyota and www.global.honda were the main websites used for the project.

Other Websites:

Other websites such as britannica.com, oica.com etc. were also used for the project to obtain relevant data.

News and other media:

Best possible news sources such as Japan Times, CNBC, BBC etc. were used to extract independent information such as events or controversies related to the company.

Limitations of sources of information:

Annual report: Annual report is a piece of information which is prepared and published by the company itself. Even if it is independently audited, the auditor mainly focuses on the financials. There is a chance that some information such as the prospects may

not be necessarily accurate or sometimes the information is true but is presented in a misleading form.

Company's website:

The information over the website is also provided by the company, which also may be biased and only the positive information may be published. There is also a chance that the it is not updated timely.

Media and other sources:

The information over the news or articles is provided by individuals and that might be an opinion of the individual. Reliability of such sources purely depends over one's intellect.

Accounting and Business techniques:

Financial Analysis

Horizontal Analysis:

It is a comparison of the financial statements of a company with the previous years and the current year being the base year. This analysis is used to observe trends by comparing the changes in numbers of percentages. (Investopedia, 2020a)

Limitations of Horizontal Analysis:

- Horizontal analysis focuses on past trends and ignores foreseeable issues which might have a huge impact over the performance of the company.
- There is a possibility that in a year where there an event occurred which was one-off, that too impacts on the decision taken by the analysis.
- In the time of inflation, there is no point in doing a horizontal analysis as it would not be like vs like comparison, unless we adjust the currency in line with the inflation. (status.net, 2020)

Ratio Analysis:

Ratio analysis is crucial tool for the company and its stakeholders to convert the numbers from the financial statement into ratios to assess the liquidity, profitability, solvency and operational efficiency. (Investopedia.com, 2020b)

Types of Ratios:

Efficiency ratios: Efficiency ratio or activity ratios assess how efficiently a company uses their assets and liabilities to generate profits. (Investopedia.com, 2020c)

Profitability ratios: They are used to assess the ability of the company to generate profits comparing the revenues with the expenses made. (Investopedia.com, 2020d)

Liquidity Ratios: This ratio shows the capability of the company to pay their short as well as long term debts. (Investopedia.com, 2020e)

Investor and Gearing Ratios: These ratios are usually used by the investors to make decision about investing, divesting, or predicting the performance of the company and shows how the company is financed(double-entry-bookkeeping.com, 2020)

Limitation of ratios:

- Ratios are based on past data; it is not necessary that the similar results will be achieved in the future years.
- The accounting policies of companies by which the ratios of the company are being compared might be different, this might give a rise to discrepancies and inconsistencies.
- One-off events may change the interpretation of the ratios such as a sale of asset which gave a rise to cash which made the ratios healthy
- Different companies have different strategies, some focus on cost, some on quality so this would not be a like vs like comparison, which would eventually

lead to wrong decision making. (Bragg, 2019a)

SWOT analysis:

SWOT stands for Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats related to a company. It is an assessment of the Strengths a company has which can be used to maintain or improve current condition, Weaknesses which the company needs to focus on, Opportunities which can be exploited to grow, Threats which the company should be cautious about.

Strengths: Strengths are the qualities a company has which gives them a competitive advantage over the competitors. Unique attributes such as a patent to manufacture a product or a certain process or any expertise.

Weaknesses: Weaknesses are the internal flaws of a company which limits them from growth or areas where the company is exposed to risks. This can be a high fixed overhead, a failure in the production process etc.

Opportunities: This is an external factor which the company could grab and enhance their growth prospects. This could be a favourable change in the regulatory system, or a technology to improve products.

Threats: Threats are an external factor which have an adverse effect over the business. A new competitor, or an adverse change by the regulatory could be a threat to the company. (Bragg, 2020a)

Limitation of SWOT Analysis:

- SWOT analysis sometimes lacks in clarity, for example a factor can be a strength and a weakness at the same time, the tool does not provide a definite solution, so the managers need to use their own judgment.
- The classification of the factors depends on the experiences of the person making it, so it makes it difficult for the managers to get an unbiased opinion.

- SWOT does not prioritize the factors itself; this makes it challenging for the managers to rank the issues.
- Once the managers have prioritized the factors, they would receive so many opinions that it would not be possible to address each one of them. (status.net, 2020)

PEST Analysis:

PEST stands for Political, Economic, Social, Technological factors that have an impact over the business externally. This analysis helps the businesses to consider and take corrective measures to deal with the changes occurring due to these factors. (Investopedia, 2020a)

Political: These can be the changes in the government, change in rules by regulatory bodies, changes in laws etc.

Economic: This part considers the economic conditions of the country such as the rate of inflation, changes in the in fiscal and monetary policies of the country.

Social: Behavioural changes of the people of a certain country, changes in taste and fashion etc. which effects the company.

Technological: Innovations, technology becoming obsolete, by which the organizations productions and strategies are affected. (Bragg, 2020b)

Limitations of PEST Analysis:

- The factors keep on changing and there is a chance that until the company takes and action, the cause of taking the action ceases to exist.
- PEST analysis also depends on the experience and judgement of the maker of the analysis, some factors which might be in the favour of the company might be classified as adverse effects.
- Finding the data is extremely challenging when it comes to practicality. Detecting problems becomes difficult for the maker in real life.

- Each topic requires a lot of research and focus. PEST analysis is quiet time consuming and the businesses would need to weigh up the cost vs benefit. (Frue, 2018)

Ethical Consideration:

The Ethical Considerations have been taken into account during the preparation of this project. All the information used is free from manipulation, accurate, relevant and reliable to the best of my knowledge. Harvard Anglia style was used for referencing to maintain the integrity. This report is for academic purposes only.

Part – 3

Analysis, Conclusion and Recommendation

Business Analysis:

SWOT Analysis:

Strengths:

- **Market Share:**

Toyota has the 2nd largest share in the automobile industry, Toyota managed to capture 11.4% of the market. This itself is a free mode of marketing and it increases reputation. (focus2move.com, 2020)

- **Innovation Capability:**

Toyota is the biggest R&D spender in the whole Japan. Toyota and JAXA (Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency) are developing manned rover to explore The Moon. (Malik, 2019)

- **Maintaining Ratios:**

Toyota maintains ideal ratios for several the current ratio, which is remarkably close to 1. This is a sign optimum utilization of working capital. The debtors are also given sufficient time, Receivable turnover days is 30 days which means Toyota gives their dealers ample time to make payments. (Annexure, Ratios)

Weaknesses:

- **Inability to meet quantity demands:**

Toyota's hybrid vehicles are in high demand, but Toyota was not able to meet the demand for Hybrid models of RAV4 and Corolla. (Dawson, 2019) The reason behind this is Toyota has 11-day supply in stock and it need 20-day stock supplies. (Bloomberg.com, 2019)

- **Vehicle Recalls:**

Toyota's vehicles were called back several times for some defaults either in the

software, braking system, or airbag systems. These recalls cost Toyota billions of dollars. These recalls have an adverse impact on the reputation of the brand as well. For example, Toyota recently recalled 3.4 million vehicles for airbag defaults. (autoblog.com, 2020)

- **Payable Turnover days:**

Toyota pays their creditors in 40 days, which is close to the inventory days. This means that Toyota makes payment to the suppliers once the inventory is sold. This might frustrate the suppliers which would have an adverse effect over long term. (Annexure, Ratios)

- **Dividend Pay-out:**

The dividend paid by Toyota to its shareholders is extremely low compared to the other competitors in the market, these might be upsetting the shareholders who prefer short-term gains rather than long term capital gains. (Annexure, Ratios)

Opportunities:

- **Self-driven vehicles:**

Market for Autonomous Cars is currently a niche market although its fast growing. Toyota is moving really slow towards self-driven cars for now. Toyota could increase their R&D expenditure to move into this market. (reuters.com, 2019)

- **Lack of Lithium Ion batteries:**

The extraction of Lithium and Cobalt which is required to produce batteries is inadequate currently (Prnewswire.com, 2019), Toyota could start amalgamate with the mining companies and start producing batteries on a large scale to regulate their supply.

Threats:

- **COVID-19:**

Vast spread of coronavirus has changed the patterns of consumer spending. It

has become exceedingly difficult for the companies to survive as every business is affected. The automobile industry has also been affected in these crucial times, Toyota and many other manufacturers have planned to shut down their production facilities. (Tchir, 2020)

- **Chinese auto-manufacturers:**

The Chinese car manufacturing companies have started capturing the market by providing cheaper vehicles in the market. If Toyota would not provide competitive prices, bulk buyers who price sensitive would move to Chinese manufacturers. (Boston, 2020)

Pest Analysis:

Political:

- **Geopolitical Issues:**

Toyota has a good demand for their vehicles in China, due to the disputes between Japan and China, Toyota had underperformed several times. For example, in 2012, anti-Japan protests took place which had an adverse effect over sales in China. (businessinsider.com, 2012)

- **CO2 Emission policies:**

All the automobile companies must maintain the CO2 emissions according to the carbon budgets set out by the government. If a company fails to do so, huge fines are levied upon them. For example, in European Union countries, companies could face a fine of €20billion if they fail to comply with the budget. (King, 2020) On the other hand, tax cuts are provided to the companies for eco-friendly, electric vehicles.

Economical:

- **Fiscal policies:**

Fiscal policies of Japan and countries in which Toyota operates have huge impact over Toyota. Like in FY2018, U.S tax windfall in which U.S had reduced their corporate tax from 33% to 21%. Since Toyota's biggest export market is

North America, Toyota enjoyed a surge of 54% in their operating profits. (Greimel, 2018)

- **Fuel prices:**

Fuel prices are correlated to the sales of automobiles. If the prices of fuel increase people either shifted to smaller vehicles or public transport and if the fuel prices are reduced the vehicles sales boom. (Unrao, 2018)

Social:

- **Taste and Fashion:**

Peoples choices for their vehicles vary depending upon the age, use, trend, and several other factors. The preferences of the customers of cars change rapidly year by year. Automobile manufacturers need to monitor the changes of the taste closely. (G, 2019)

- **Electric Cars:**

People nowadays have become aware of the effects of global warming caused by CO2 emissions, due to which a lot of people are trying to purchase eco-friendly vehicles. Experts believe that 20 years down the line, 50% of the cars sold will be electric. (edition.cnn.com, 2019)

Technological:

- **Charging points:**

Fully Electric vehicles require charging points which are not available in many countries, this is the reason people are reluctant to buy E-vehicles. If the charging points increase around the globe, the demand for fully electric vehicles would increase. (Ulrich, 2020)

- **Batteries for Electric Cars:**

The focus of the consumers moving towards fully Electronic cars is high but there is still need of improvements of batteries for the vehicles. Advancement of the batteries would make them long lasting, hence people would not hesitate to buy Electric vehicles. (Langridge, 2020)

Financial Analysis:

Horizontal Analysis

Sales Chart

(Toyota Annual Report 2017,2018, 2019)

In the Year 2017, the sales had fallen by 2.84% (Annexure, FS). Although the number of vehicles sold in 2017 were higher as compared to 2016, this was first time in 5 years that the revenues had fallen even if the number of vehicles sold in 2017 were higher than 2016. The reason for the fall was mainly the adverse exchange rate fluctuations. (AFP, 2017b)

However in the year 2018, revenue increased from ¥27597.1million to ¥29,379.5million that is 6.46%(Annexure, FS) the main reason behind this increase were the favourable currency movements (Parashar, 2018a) and also increase in the average price of Toyota vehicles per unit globally. (Irvine, 2019)

The sales from 2018 to 2019 had increased by 2.88%, the primary reason behind this increase was increase in the sales volume in Asia-Pacific and Europe due to increased

demand of RAV4 and Corolla Hybrid models. (Team, 2019) Also due to the trade war in the U.S, there was an average increase of \$3000 per vehicle. (Ferris, 2018)

(Toyota, Annual report, 2017, 2018, 2019)

Japan:

Revenue for Toyota increased from ¥14,830million to ¥16,024billion in 2018 and ¥16625.30b in 2019, the sales grew 0.5%, 8.1% and 3.7% respectively. (Annexure, FS). Stability in the economy of Japan had caused this increase in the year 2018. (Parashar, 2018a)

North America:

Toyota’s biggest international customer base is North America (Parashar, 2016b), the sales in North America have remained almost constant with an increase of 5.64% from 2017 to 2019.

Europe:

However, Toyota performed well in Europe by an increase of 0.7% in the revenues. When all the other regions have shown a fall in revenues. This was due to increased

sale of Hybrid EV vehicles Yaris, RAV4 which increased by 38% and Toyota reached 1 million mark of units sold. (newsroom.toyota.eu, 2018)

Asia:

Sales in Asia for Toyota has also grown from 2017 to 2018 increased by 6.81%, this increase was caused by the price hike of 3% by Toyota in India. (Mukherjee & Thakkar, 2017)

Toyota sold around 8,964,000 units all over the globe, this was 0.07% lesser units compared to the previous year. However, the revenues increased by ¥1782.3million which is 6.5% in the year 2018. The reason in the (Parashar, 2018b) (Toyota Financial Summary, 2018).

Comparison with Competitor:

(Toyota, Honda annual report, 2017, 2018, 2019)

2017 was a harsh year for Honda as their revenue had fallen by 4.1% and stood at ¥13999.2million. (Honda Annual report, 2017) Despite good performance by the company in terms of sales units internationally but in the main market, U.S. the sales volume declined by 7% in Honda and 12% in Acura this fall was first time in 7 years.

(Phillips, 2018)

Revenues for Honda increased from 13,999.2 million to 15,361 million which comes to 9.7% from 2017 to 2018, (Annexure, IS). Increase in the price by Honda across all of their models of cars and motorcycles by 3% in India. (Reuters.com, 2016) A total of 3.1% increase in the overall unit sales mainly due to increase in the sale of Civic. (Shaikh, 2018)

For FY 2019, Honda's Revenue increased by ¥527,471 million which is 3.43% increase as compared to the previous year. (Annexure, IS) This was caused due to increase in the car prices by 4.2% in the U.S. (Schultz, 2019)

Ratio Analysis:

Profitability Ratios:

Operating Profit Margin:

Operating Profit Margin (OPM) is a metric to measure the profits company makes from its operations. (Kenton, 2020)

(Annexure, Ratios)

2017:

In the Year 2017, Toyota’s profits had fallen for the first time in 5 years. (bbc.com, 2017). The profit of ¥1,994.3million stood at 30.1% lower from 2016. The reason for the fall Toyota gave was higher costs and currency fluctuations Sales had fallen in Toyota’s main market, North America by 1.08% whereas their sales got increased by 4.7%. (efe.com, 2018)

A new manufacturing process lead to saving of ¥100billion to Toyota in the middle of

FY 2017. But this money was later on injected into research and development of electrified power trains and Artificial Intelligence. (Buckland & Sao, 2017)

Toyota was expecting a further decline in their profits in 2018 due to strengthening of JPY against USD. (bbc.com, 2017c) for Toyota the Operating profits grew by 20.33% (Annexure, Ratios). The operating costs increased by 5.37% which is lower compared to the increase of 6.45% of revenue. The decrease in operating costs caused by recently introduced production system which uses standardized parts that can be used for several models. (Tajitsu, 2018)

Toyota's operating profits were increased by ¥67,683million which 2.88% increase and it did not bring any significant change to the operating margin which stayed at 8.16%. The reason behind this is the costs for Camry had increased \$1800 per unit in the U.S due to increased import tariffs. (Lippert, 2018)

Honda's Operating profits increased ¥840.7million in 2017 which is 67.0% increase compared to the previous year. Despite and increase in sales units, Honda managed to reduce their direct costs by 6.66%. (Annexure, IS) This increase was driven by increase in unit sales due to changes in the design of vehicles specifically Honda Pilot (Jenkins, 2017) and motorcycles, reduction in selling and other costs.

For Honda, in the FY 2018 the revenue had increased by 9.72% but the operating profit had fallen to by 0.85% which caused the operating profit margin to fall 6.01% to 5.43%. (Annexure, IS). This fall occurred because the Japanese Yen got strengthened and high research and development cost. (Tajitsu, 2017)

In FY2019 the operating profits of Honda had fallen by 12.86% which brought down the OPM further to 4.57%. Revenues increased by 3.43% but but the operating costs increased by 4.36% which which caused the fall. (Annexure, IS). The reason of this fall was changes in the global automobile production network and adverse currency fluctuation. (Honda, 2019)

Net Profit Margin:

Net Profit Margin (NPM) indicates the percentage of profits remaining after deducting all the expenses from the revenue. (Bragg, 2019b)

(Annexure, Ratios)

In FY 2017, the net profits had also declined by ¥507,226million which is 20.84% lesser than the previous year. The operating profits were 30.12% lower but gains in foreign exchange, increase in interest and dividend income helped the NPM to stay less deteriorated, the net income fell by 20.83%. The Foreign exchange gains increased by 702% (Annexure, IS).

In the FY 2018, the net profits increased by ¥426,604million which is 19.44% growth compared to previous year. (Annexure IS). The major reason for this increase was increased operating profits due to U.S tax cuts and Jobs Act and favourable currency movements. (dallasnews.com, 2017).

The profits would be even higher but Toyota had to recall 2.4 million hybrid vehicles in 2018 for faulty systems. (bbc.com, 2018) Recalls cost a lot of expenditure to the company which effects the company's profits. One of the Toyota dealers accused Toyota for they had incurred \$15.8 million for a safety-recall software. (Favot, 2019)

Toyota's net income fell by ¥600,519million which is 23.22% despite the increase in operating income, this brought down the NPM to 6.57%. (Annexure, IS). The reason for this fall was unrealized losses on securities caused by market deterioration and the one time gains of ¥250billion caused by US tax reform made the profits look adverse. (Agence France-Presse, 2019)

On the other hand, Honda's net profit, like their operating profits in 2017 increased by ¥273,036million which is 67.69% compared to previous year, Honda had made a loss of ¥78,980million in the final quarter of 2016 this loss was caused due to Honda Takata recall for the airbag issues. (bbc.com, 2016) this is the exact percentage by which the operating profits increased which denotes that there was no change in the other expenses. (Honda Financial Summary, 2017)

In FY2018 Honda's operating profits had decreased by 0.9% but the net profits increased by ¥44,9245million which is 66% more than the previous year.(Annexure, IS) . The main elements which caused this increase were increased profits from investments accounted for using equity method, lower finance costs and reduction in the corporate taxes in U.S. (Greimel, 2018)

FY2019: The operating profits decreased further for by 12.86% which also impacted the net profits. The net profits for the fiscal year reduced by ¥45,2353million which is 40% lessor compared to the previous year. (Annexure, IS) The fall in this was because of recalls due to defective airbags which costed Honda ¥168billion. (Schultz, 2019)

Return on Capital Employed:

Return on capital employed is a ratio used to evaluate the efficiency of the capital being invested in the business. (E, 2018)

(Annexure, Ratios)

Toyota 2017: The ROCE had reduced from 7.77% to 6.13% this fell due to the drastic fall of profits in 2017. The capital employed had increased by only 0.4%. (Annexure, IS&FS) This was when the profits had fallen for the first time in 5 years due to huge currency fluctuations. (bbc.com, 2017).

Toyota 2017-2018: The ROCE increased by 29.75% this was due to tremendous increase in profits of 426,604 million JPY which is 19.44%. (Annexure, Ratios). This was caused due to exceptional increase of the profits due to U.S tax cuts and Jobs Act. (Toyota annual report, 2019)

In the year 2019 Toyota's fell even more to 5.89% due to net income had reduced by 23%. Due to the reversal effect of the previous years one-off surge of 19.44% of the net profit. Similarly, the equity and the liabilities also had increased 3.28% and 4.41% respectively. (Annexure, FS)

Honda 2017: Honda's ROCE increased by 54.46% in 2017, in 2016, the ROCE was 3.25% and went up to 5.02% in 2017. (Honda annual report, 2017) In 2016, the profit

margin was exceptionally low which caused the ROCE fall. This fall was due to the loss Honda made in the last quarter of 2016 due to Honda Takata recall for airbag default. (bbc.com, 2016)

Honda FY 2018: The ROCE jumped from 5.02 to 8.22 which is 63.75% increase, this was due to increase in net profits due to U.S tax cuts and Jobs Act. (Honda newsroom, 2018). Another reason is that the equity had also increased by ¥664,469 million which is an increase of 8.77% up compared to the previous year. This was increased due to higher retained earnings. (Honda Fincial Summary, 2018)

Honda FY 2019: The ROCE reduced to 4.68% which a fall of 43.04%, this is because the net profits decreased by ¥452,353million to ¥676,286million which is 40% reduction. (Annexure, IS) The reason behind this fall is the one-off surge of profits in FY2018 which caused the ROCE increase. Another reason for the decrease in ROCE is the increase in equity and non-current liabilities by 4.025% and 6.94% respectively. (Honda Financial Summary, 2019)

Liquidity Ratios:

Current Ratio:

Current ratio is calculated to assess the ability of the company to pay the short term debts. (Investopedia.com, 2020g)

(Annexure, Ratios)

Toyota 2017: The current ratio for the 2017 was 1.03 which is 8.85% lessor than the previous year, in 2016 the current ratio stood at 1.13 (Toyota Financial Summary, 2017). The decrease in 2017 was caused because no deferred tax asset this year and decrease in prepaid expenses by ¥537,048million. (Toyota Financial Summary, 2017)

Toyota 2018: The Current Ratio decreased by 0.94% and came down to 1.02 times. Even though the current assets of the company were increased by 1.79%, the current liabilities were increased by a bigger margin of 2.76%. (Toyota Financial Summary, 2018).

Toyota FY2019: The current ratio increased to 1.04 which is 1.55% as compared to the previous year. This increase was caused by a huge increase in cash of ¥522,435million which is 17.11% as compared to the previous year, the reason behind this increase was that Toyota dumped 36.26% of their marketable securities (Cho, 2019), due to this the overall current assets had increased by 4% and the liabilities had increased only by 2.4%. (Toyota Financial Summary, 2019)

Honda 2017: For Honda, the current ratio for the 2016 was 1.14 times, then in year

2017 it increased by 6% and came to 1.21. the reason behind this was the total current assets had increased by 5.02%, this was caused by an increase mainly in cash and cash equivalents of 19.83%. The current liabilities had also reduced by 0.72% in that year. (Honda Financial Summary, 2017)

Honda 2018: The current ratio had increased by 1.97% and came up to 1.23. The increase in total current assets of 5.64% this was mainly due to increased Inventory, financial services receivables and foreign exchange currency fluctuations despite a decrease in cash and cash equivalents. The liabilities had also increased by 3.6% (Honda newsroom, 2018)

Honda 2019: The current ratio remained constant in this year. The total current assets had increased by 6.09% but the liabilities had also increased by similar percentage of 6.02% which made the current ratio to remain constant. (Honda Financial Summary, 2019)

Activity Ratios:

Debtor Turnover Days:

Debtor Turnover days is a formula used to calculate the average days it takes for the debtors to make the payment from the purchase date. (Wallstreetmojo.com, 2020)

(Annexure, Ratios)

The Debt turnover ratio for the financial years 2017 and 2018 was 30 days. This is an ideal credit limit provided in any industry. Toyota’s trade debtors are mostly the dealers who retail their vehicles.

Honda’s debtor turnover days is lesser as compared to Toyota. Honda has sells around 20 million motorcycles every year. Motorcycles are fast moving products as compared to Cars and SUVs which is why the consumer mostly does not go for financing options and the retailers make the payment quickly. Honda’s debtor days has reduced from 20 days in FY 2017 to 19 days in FY 2018 and 18 days in FY 2019. The reason behind this fall is that the sales are increasing more than the trade payables. (Annexure, IS and FS)

Inventory Turnover Days:

Inventory Turnover days is ratio calculated to analyse the time it takes to sell the products after it is ready for sale. (finstanon.com, 2020)

(Annexure, Ratios)

The Industry average of the inventory turnover days for the 3 financial years, FY2017,2018 and 2019 were 30, 30 and 21 days, respectively. (csimarket.com, 2020) For Toyota, the Inventory turnover has not changed significantly in any of these financial years. (Annexure, IS and FS). Toyota’s Inventory days were always high compared to the industry average, this indicates that Toyota has some slow-moving inventory, or the inventory has become obsolete.

Toyota inventory days in 2017 were increased to 40 from 35 days in 2016. (Toyota Annual report, 2017) The reason for this increase was Toyota’s higher production of Toyota Tacoma increase by 60% (Stocksdale, 2016).

Honda’s Inventory days has been constant as well in 3 years after the increase of inventory days in 2017.

However, Honda’s Inventory days are slightly closer to the industry average as they sell motorcycles too and they are fast moving products. (Annexure, IS and FS).

Creditor Turnover Days:

Creditor turnover days is calculated to estimate the duration company takes to pay

their creditors over and accounting period. (corporatefinanceinstitute.com, 2020)

(Annexure, Ratios)

For Toyota, in FY 2017, the creditor turnover days stood at 43 days, this was an increase of 2 days compared to the previous year (Toyota, annual report, 2017) The reason for this increase was increased cost of production due to increased prices of steel by 38%. (Heeb, 2018)

The Credit turnover days is gradually decreasing a day year by year. This is extremely slow but might be satisfactory for the suppliers of Toyota.

Honda's Creditor turnover days was reduced by 6 days from 2017 to 2019, this decrease was caused due to the increased cost of sales, the increase in the cost of sales was due to the increase of prices of steel which consists of 47% of the material used in cars. (Heeb, 2018)

Investors Ratios:

EPS (Earnings Per Share):

EPS is a ratio which shows the amount of the earnings of the company which are available for the average number of existing shares. (corporatefinanceinstitute.com, 2020)

(Annexure, Others)

In 2017, Toyota suffered a decrease of ¥481.5million in profits attributable to shareholders which is 20.8% less compared to the previous year. Which had caused the EPS to fall from ¥741.36 to ¥605.47.

In 2018, the EPS boosted to ¥842 from ¥605.47. This was caused by increase in the net income attributable to common shareholders increased by ¥662,874m. This was due to exceptional increase of the net profits 34.2% caused by U.S tax cuts. (Toyota Newsroom, 2018) In this year, the shares had increased by 22.47%, if this would not have happened, the EPS would have been much higher. (Toyota Financial Summary, 2018)

In the year 2019, Toyota's EPS have fallen back to 650.55, this was a decrease of 22.73% but this was due to the profits fall due to the reversal effect of the profits made in 2018 due to U.S tax deductions. (Greimel, 2018)

Honda's EPS was also remained at similar level except in 2018 where the EPS increased to ¥590.79 due to exceptional increases in profits In 2018. The number of shares have reduced by 2.1% in the 3 year period.

P/E Ratio:

Price/Earnings ratio determines the value of the share of the company. It is calculated to compare the value of the of different companies. (investopedia.com, 2020j)

(Annexure, Ratios)

Toyota's P/E ratio in the year 2017 was 19.91 which is was reduced in the year 2018 due to high price of the shares which was \$130.37 (Annexure, Others), this came after the announcement of the \$10B expenditure over expansion. (cnbc, 2017)

In the year 2019, Honda's P/E ratio had become a little stable and came to 8.7 times.

The market price in the year 2019 had fallen from \$34.42 to \$27.17 due to the announcement of closure of their only British car plant in 2022 due to declining demand for diesel vehicles and Brexit. (Minkoff, 2019)

Dividend Yield:

Dividend yield is a ratio which shows how much percentage of the market price the company pays to its shareholders. (Investopedia.com, 2020h)

(Annexure, Ratios)

Toyota pays out a constant dividend, the dividend paid by Toyota in 2017 was ¥210 which had increased by ¥10 compared to 2016.(Toyota annual report, 2017) The Market price for Toyota in 2017 was \$108.62 which was \$106.32 in 2016. (finance.yahoo.com, 2020a)

Toyota’s Market price took a boost in 2018 and jumped straight to \$130.37 from \$108.62 (finance.yahoo.com, 2020a), this hike of 20% forced the dividend yield to reduce by 27 basis points. This increase caused the dividend yield to come down 1.79% from 1.89%. (Annexure, Ratios). This unexpected increase was caused due to

the announcement of \$billion in 5 years in the U.S. (cnbc, 2017)

Toyota on an average pays exceptionally low dividend as compared to the other competitors. (economictimes.com, 2017)

Toyota's Dividend yield came back to 1.68% as the stock price reduced by 9.47% and came down to \$118.02. (finance.yahoo.com, 2020a)

Market price for Honda in 2017 was \$30.26 in 2017 (finance.yahoo.com, 2020b) and it reduced to \$27.17 in the year 2019 which caused the increase of dividend yield. Honda pays a dividend of around 30% of the EBITDA. (Reuters.com, 2017)

Gearing Ratios:

Financial Gearing:

Financial gearing ratio shows the proportions of finance used by the company, i.e. How much raised through equity, how much is raised through debt. (Investopedia.com, 2020i)

(Annexure, Ratios)

Toyota's financial gearing in FY2017 had increased from 77.2% to 78.11% which is 1.18% increase as compared to the previous year. This increase was due to Toyota investment plans of \$10billion in the U.S. in 5 years to increase production facilities. (cnbc, 2017)

The financial gearing had reduced by 6.48% and came down to 73.04% in FY2018, the gearing was reduced high increase in retained earnings of ¥1,872,349m which came in due to high profits by tax windfall in the U.S. (Greimel, 2018)

The financial gearing changed only by a small percentage of 0.74% in 2019, the reason behind this is Toyota's long term debt increased by ¥544,571m and a massive increase in the retained earnings of ¥2,514,051m which is 12.9% increase compared to the previous year. (Annexure, Ratios)

Honda's Financial gearing had been high in 2017, but since Honda is a capital-intensive company, it is not an issue to have a high gearing as long as they are able to make their interest and debt payments. (Parashar, 2016)

Interest Cover:

Interest Cover Ratio is calculated to assess the ability of the company to pay their interests. (readyratios.com, 2020)

(Annexure, Ratios)

For the year 2017, Toyota’s interest cover was decreased from 93 times to 88 times (Toyota annual report, 2017), the reason behind this was the fall of 21% in the net income of Toyota in 2017 which was due to stronger Yen against dollar and other currencies. (AFP, 2017a)

Toyota’s Interest cover in the FY2018 jumped to 113 times which was caused by exceptional increase of the profits due to U.S tax windfall. (Greimel, 2018) Later in the year 2019 it came back to 95 times. Interest cover of Toyota is strong as they their finance costs are remarkably low as compared to their profits.

Honda’s Interest Cover is also extremely healthy but they have been reduced except in FY2018 due to one-off profit surge. Other than that, the interest cover has been reduced to 75 due to falling profits of Honda. (Annexure, Ratios)

Conclusion

The automobile industry has big players in it and Toyota is one of them. Toyota has shown constant growth from year 2017, 2018 and 2019. Toyota worked hard each

financial year to maintain their position in the industry where the competition is fierce.

Toyota's Sales have constantly grown from 2017 to 2018 6.48% and 2.88% from 2018 to 2019. Over the years they have managed to make a good customer base around the globe, being North America is the biggest market for their vehicles.

Toyota has several Strengths which they can use to grab the opportunities available to them such as scale and size of their organisation, They have extremely dangerous threat of sales fall due to COVID-19 pandemic. Retained earnings would now play a big role for to retain their competent staff and production facilities.

Toyota profitability ratios were healthy throughout the three-year period as the they have grown their OPM and net profits margins each year. Most of the fluctuations were caused by the foreign exchange movements. However, the profits have grown overall except the NPM which declined in 2019 which was due a reversal effect of exceptional surge in of NPM in 2018.

Liquidity ratios of Toyota had also remained healthy and constant as the current ratio remained above 1 but remarkably close to 1 indicating the working capital is being utilized to the optimum. The quick ratio was above the industry average, it puts a good impression over lenders, but it is also an indication of underutilization of the cash and cash equivalents.

Activity ratios are the area where Toyota could do better as the inventory days were higher than the industry average indicating that they have slow moving inventory. 43 Creditor days are also high, but they are decreasing very slowly. Delayed payments could frustrate the suppliers and cause inconsistencies.

The EPS had grown tremendously in 2018 due to exception increase of profits and came down to the average rate of Toyota in 2019. The one-off increased profits in 2018 also had an impact over P/E ratio as it caused it to reduce in 2018 later in 2019 the P/E stabilized too. Toyota pays out a constant dividend which kept the dividend

yield constant over the years.

Toyota was 78% geared in 2017 but later in 2018 they reduced the gearing to 73% and it remained the same in 2019. Toyota's Interest Cover is very healthy 2018 profit surge effect caused it to cross 100 times but in 2019 it came back to normal.

By constantly innovating and spending more on R&D, Toyota can retain their position in the automobile industry.

Recommendations:

- Focusing more over fully electric vehicles would help Toyota to be competitive in the market.
- Currency fluctuations cause a lot of discrepancies in the profits. Better Foreign exchange risk management could help them reduce this.
- Increasing the production capacity to meet the demands for hybrid vehicles would help them retain brand loyalty of their customers.
- Improving their designing and manufacturing systems to reduce the risk of errors in production which could help Toyota to reduce recall costs.